

blank; n = moles of N-bromosaccharin equivalent to one mole of sample; M = molecular weight of the sample and N = molarity of sodium thiosulphate solution.

Results and Discussion

It was found that the reaction is complete after 5 minutes in case of methyl red and methyl orange and 10 minutes in case of congo red and chrysoidine, consuming 5, 5, 2 and 2 moles of N-bromosaccharin respectively.

The method may conveniently be applied to any other azo dye having an activated phenyl ring. The estimation of azo-benzene has not been possible even under more rigorous reaction condition. The inertness is probably due to the absence of a ring activating group. It was also observed that the presence of acetic acid was essential for better ionisation of the reagent and a two times excess of the reagent gives accurate results.

References

1. R. D. TIWARI and J. P. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 173.
2. T. S. MA and J. V. EARLEY, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1959, 129.
3. J. V. EARLEY and T. S. MA, *Mikrochim Acta*, 1960, 685.
4. U. C. PANDEY and M. GOPAL, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 328.
5. N. K. MATHUR and J. M. BACHHAWAT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1335.

Azine Dyes as Spot Test Reagents†

N. VENKATESWARA RAO and P. V. RAMANA

Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 12 June 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

THE azine dyes that have been used in spot test analysis are: Neutral Red, Phenosafranine, Methylene Violet, Amethyst Violet, Safranin T, Wool Fast Blue BL and Aposafraanine. Neutral Red has been employed for the detection of nitrite¹ and chlorine², whereas, Safranin T has been utilised for the detection of sugar in urine³, nitrite, nitrous acid⁴, perchlorate⁵ and hypohalites⁶. Safranin T, Phenosafranine, Methylene Violet, Amethyst Violet, Wool Fast Blue BL and Aposafraanine have been used for the detection of palladium(II)⁷ and sulphite, hypophosphite and ascorbic acid⁸. The present paper describes the use of the azine dyes. Neutral Violet, Neutral Red, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine (Colour Index Nos. 50030, 50040, 50085, 50090, 50320 and 50420 respectively) as reagents for the

spot test detection of osmium(VIII), arsenic(III) and iodide. The advantages of these reagents are: (1) the tests are very sensitive and (2) the tests are not vitiated by the presence of small amounts of related substances.

Experimental

A standard solution (0.01 M) of arsenic(III) was prepared from E. Merck 'pro analysi' sample of arsenious oxide. Approximately 0.01 M solutions of osmium(VIII) (J and M sample), potassium bromate and potassium iodide (B. D. H. AnalaR samples) were prepared and standardised.

Solutions of the dyes (0.01%) were prepared in deionised water from the following samples:— Neutral Violet: George T. Gurr; Neutral Red: E. Merck; Azocarmine G and Nigrosine: Fluka; Azocarmine B: E. Gurr; Wool Fast Blue GL: Bayer.

The solutions were suitably diluted whenever necessary.

The following procedures are adapted for the detection of the different ions.

Detection of osmium(VIII): One drop (0.05 ml) of the dye solution (0.002% in the case of Neutral Violet and Neutral Red and 0.01% in the case of the other four dyes) is taken in the depression of a spot plate and treated with 2 drops (0.10 ml) of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, 2 drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate and 3 drops of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ arsenic(III) solutions [2 drops of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ arsenic(III) solution while using Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine]. One drop of the test solution is then added to this mixture and the discharge of the colour of the solution indicates the presence of osmium(VIII).

Detection of arsenic(III): One drop of the dye solution (0.002% in the case of Neutral Violet and Neutral Red and 0.01% in the case of the remaining four dyes), two drops of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, two drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate, one drop of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ osmium(VIII) solutions and three drops of deionised water are taken in the depression of a spot plate and mixed well. One drop of the test solution of arsenic(III) is then added and the solution mixed thoroughly. An immediate disappearance of the dye colour indicates the presence of arsenic(III).

Detection of iodide: One drop of 0.002% Neutral Violet or Neutral Red solution (the remaining four dyes are not suitable in this test) is mixed with two drops of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sulphuric acid, two drops of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ potassium bromate, one drop of the test (iodide) solution, one drop of deionised water and two drops of $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ arsenic(III) solution, in

† Presented at the National Symposium on Microchemical Techniques, Mysore, May 16-18, 1980.

the depression of a spot plate. One drop of $1 \times 10^{-7} M$ osmium(VIII) solution is then added to the above mixture. Under these conditions, the colour of the solution does not disappear even in 15 min, whereas, in the absence of iodide, the colour of the solution disappears almost instantaneously.

The identification and dilution limits for the three tests are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION AND DILUTION LIMITS		
Dye(s)	Identification Limit, $\mu\text{g}/0.5 \text{ ml}$	Dilution Limit
<i>Detection of osmium(VIII)</i>		
Neutral Violet and Neutral Red Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B and Wool Fast Blue GL	9×10^{-4}	$1 : 5.5 \times 10^4$
Nigrosine	0.03	$1 : 5.5 \times 10^6$
<i>Detection of arsenic(III)</i>		
Neutral Violet, Neutral Red, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine	0.80	$1 : 1.6 \times 10^6$
<i>Detection of iodide</i>		
Neutral Violet and Neutral Red ^a	0.01	$1 : 5.0 \times 10^7$

^a The other four dyes are not suitable in this test.

Interferences : The tests are not vitiated by the presence of the following ions.

Detection of osmium(VIII) : $\text{Ru}^{3+} : 0.05 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Pt}^{2+} : 0.9 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Pd}^{2+} : 0.5 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Au}^{3+} : 0.9 \mu\text{g}$.

Detection of arsenic(III) : $\text{Sb}^{5+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Sn}^{4+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Cd}^{2+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Pb}^{2+} : 0.10 \text{ mg}$.

Detection of iodide : $\text{F}^- : 0.01 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Cl}^- : 0.17 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Br}^- : 0.4 \text{ mg}$; $\text{SCN}^- : 0.03 \text{ mg}$.

Results and Discussion

In our studies on the use of these azine dyes as indicators in the bromatometric titration of arsenic(III) at low concentrations of sulphuric acid and using osmium(VIII) as catalyst⁹, we have observed that the osmium(VIII)-catalysed arsenic(III)-bromate reaction accelerates the slow reaction between the dye and bromate. Based on this observation, we have developed a method for the kinetic-catalytic determination of osmium(VIII)¹⁰. The spot test detections of osmium(VIII) and arsenic(III) are governed by the above-mentioned principle. In our method for the kinetic-catalytic determination of osmium(VIII), we have found that the decolouration of the dyes, Neutral Violet and Neutral Red,

is inhibited in the presence of iodide, and this is the principle underlying the detection of iodide, now reported.

References

1. I. M. KORENMAN and V. I. YUMINA, *Trudy Khim. i. Khim. Tekhnol.*, 1958, **1**, 144.
2. S. ELLIOTT and J. ROY, *Army Med. Corps.*, 1957, **103**, 74.
3. H. MACLEAN, *Biochem. J.*, 1907, **2**, 431.
4. P. CARBONI, *Chimica e industria*, 1954, **36**, 825.
5. N. A. BILAK, *Sbornik Khim. Fak.*, 1954, **4**, 87.
6. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 6th ed., 1972, p. 149.
7. N. V. RAO and K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 788.
8. N. V. RAO and K. M. M. KRISHNA PRASAD, 67th session of the Indian Science Congress, Calcutta, Feb. 1-5, 1980.
9. N. V. RAO and P. V. RAMANA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1977, **285**, 125.
10. N. V. RAO and P. V. RAMANA, 8th International Microchemical Symposium, Graz, Austria, Aug. 25-30, 1980 (accepted for presentation).

Studies on the Dielectric Constants of O/W Emulsions Stabilized by Surfactants

TRILOK CHAND and P. K. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. (P. G.) College, Dehradun-248 001 (U.P.)

Manuscript received 23 November 1979, revised 27 August 1980, accepted 1 November 1980

A survey of literature reveals that a number of studies have been carried out experimentally and theoretically on the dielectric properties of colloidally or coarsely dispersed systems¹⁻³. The influence of frequency range⁴, agitation⁵, shear⁶ and temperature⁷ effect has also been studied.

But no attempts have yet been made to study the dielectric constants of kerosene/water and emulsions stabilized with anionic, cationic and non-ionic surfactants under the influence of emulsifier concentration, phase volume ratio, emulsification time and temperature. So the communication will provide the systematic data of dielectric constants of kerosene/water emulsions under the influence of above variables.

Experimental

Materials : Double distilled kerosene oil having sp. gr. 0.7948 g/ml was stored for use in all the experiments. Double distilled water (conductance, $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was employed throughout the course of the investigation. Sodium dioctyl sulpho succinate (Manoxol IB-anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC-cationic surfactant) and